

MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF ZANCHOR REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The Zanchor process is a through-thickness reinforcement technique that involves the use of special needles. The mode II fracture toughness of a Zanchor reinforcement composite was investigated using an end notched flexure (ENF) specimen under high loading rates. A strain distribution transition (SDT) analysis was proposed to obtain the crack growth behavior from the surface strain around the crack tip. A finite element analysis was performed to verify that SDT analysis estimated the crack growth behavior accurately under impact loading. The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the Zanchor composite was studied by static and impact ENF tests. For the impact test, a split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) system was used, and a stress wave controlling (SWC) technique was employed to decrease the dynamic effect resulting from the inertia force. The mode II fracture toughness was calculated from the local strain based (LSB) formula. The experimental results showed that the Zanchor process improved the mode II fracture toughness under both impact and static loading. In addition, the efficiency of the Zanchor reinforcement was higher under impact loading than under static loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been extensively used in various industrial products because of their superior properties, such as a high stiffness, high strength, and low weight. However, the interlaminar strength of composite materials is inadequate, and hence, a number of studies have aimed to improve this property [1].

The Zanchor process is a through-thickness reinforcement technique, as shown in Fig. 1 [2,3]. In the Zanchor process, in-plane fibers are oriented in a through-thickness direction by a sticking process using a set of specially designed needles. Additional fibers are not required for this process. The mechanical properties of the Zanchor composites under static loading have been reported in detail in previous studies [2,3]. If the crack in the laminate propagates, the oriented out-of-plane fiber bundles, entangled fiber bundles (EFBs), bear the load until the EFB breaking strength is reached. Therefore, the mode II fracture toughness of the Zanchor composite is greater than that of the CFRP composite. However, the mechanical properties under impact loading are unknown.

In this study, the mode II impact fracture behavior of the Zanchor composites was experimentally studied to determine the effectiveness of the Zanchor reinforcement at high loading rates. The stress wave controlling (SWC) technique and local strain based (LSB) formula were used to obtain the dynamic energy release rate [4]. Strain distribution transition (SDT) analysis was also used to obtain the dynamic crack growth behavior. The validity of the estimation method was also discussed.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of the Zanchor process.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

CF/epoxy composite panels (STS-24K/RTM6, Toho Tenax/Hexcel) were fabricated in a stacking sequence of $[(0/90)_4/(90/0)_4]_s$ using an RTM process. The Zanchor process was applied to the dry preforms of STS-24K prior to the RTM process. Two types of composite panels with different Zanchor densities, Z1 and Z2, were fabricated to study the effect of the Zanchor density, Z. For comparison, composite panels without applying the Zanchor process, B0, were also fabricated using the same materials.

2.2 Quasi-static ENF and impact ENF tests

The mode II fracture behavior was studied using the end notched flexure (ENF) specimen shown in Fig. 2. The distributed type of the strain gauges was used to obtain the crack growth behavior of the specimen. The width, b , thickness, $2h$, and bending span, $2L$, of the specimen were 10, 7, and 100 mm, respectively. The crack length, a , was set to 37 mm at the start of testing to promote stable crack growth.

Quasi-static ENF tests were employed at loading rates of $d\delta/dt = 1$ mm/min. Dynamic ENF tests were conducted at loading rates of $d\delta/dt = 5-10$ m/s, using a split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) system, as shown in Fig. 3. The stress waves were measured by storing the signals of the strain gauges attached to the input bar in a digital storage oscilloscope through differential amplifiers. The surface strain of the specimen was also measured to obtain the crack growth and estimate the energy release rate, G_{II} . The SWC technique [4] was employed for suppressing the high-frequency vibration of the specimen.

Figure 2: End notched flexure specimen.

Figure 3: Split Hopkinson pressure bar system.

2.3 Data reduction

For the quasi-static fracture tests, the mode II energy release rate, G_{II} , was calculated from the reaction force of the loading point, P , by

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2 a^2 C}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)}, \quad (1)$$

where C is the value of the compliance, $C (= \delta/P)$, of the specimen.

For the impact fracture tests, the mode II energy release rate, G_{II} , was calculated from the surface strain of the specimen, ε_{sf} , by

$$G_{II} = \frac{9\varepsilon_{sf}^2 a^2 C}{2bD^2(2L^3 + 3a^3)}, \quad (2)$$

where D is the value of the strain coefficient, $D (= \varepsilon_{sf}/P)$, of the specimen. This method is effective for determining impact fracture toughness and is referred to as the LSB formula. [4]

3 ESTIMATING CRACK PROPAGATION

3.1 Strain distribution transition analysis

A cracked beam of width b , thickness $2h$, and initial crack length a_0 , as shown in Fig. 4, was considered. A bending moment was applied to the upper and lower sections of the beam. Here, ε_1 , ε_2 , and ε_3 are the surface strain of the beam around the crack tip and are used for the calculation.

Fig. 5 shows the strain distribution around the crack tip obtained by the FEM analyses. The abscissa represents the position from the crack tip, ζ . The ordinate represents the normalized surface strains by the bending moment, ε_{sf}/M . The black, red, and blue lines show the strain distributions for $\Delta a = 0, 5$, and 10 mm, respectively, where Δa is the crack extension length. As shown in the figure, the distribution of the surface strain shifts in the direction of crack growth without changing the distribution shape. Thus, the crack growth behavior can be estimated by measuring the surface strain, ε_1 , ε_2 , and ε_3 .

Figure 4: Beam including delamination.

Figure 5: Transition of the normalized strain distribution with crack extension (FEM results).

3.2 Verification of the SDT analysis

To study the feasibility of the SDT analysis, FEM analyses were conducted considering the crack growth behavior. Fig. 6 shows the FEM model of the ENF specimen. Static and impact simulations were performed, where the width, b , thickness, $2h$, bending span, $2L$, and initial crack length, a_0 , of the specimen were 10, 7, 100, and 37 mm, respectively. Four-node plane stress elements were used. A fixed displacement of 2 mm was applied to the central loading point of the specimen. The displacement rate for the impact simulation was $d\delta/dt = 10$ m/s. The crack growth behavior was simulated by a virtual crack closure (VCC) technique assuming the mode II fracture toughness $G_{IIC} = 2$ kJ/m². The material properties are listed in Table 1.

Figs. 7 (a) and (b) show the static and impact simulation results, respectively. The abscissa represents the displacement, δ , and the ordinate represents the crack length, a . The blue lines show the actual crack length, a_{true} , simulated with the VCC technique, and the red circles show the crack length, a_{SDT} , obtained by the SDT analysis. The crack length obtained by the SDT analysis, a_{SDT} , was in agreement with the actual crack length, a_{true} . Therefore, the SDT analysis effectively obtained the crack growth behavior under impact loading as well as under static loading.

Figure 6: ENF model and boundary conditions.

E_{xx} [GPa]	E_{yy} [GPa]	G_{xy} [GPa]	ν_{xy}
135	7.2	3.6	0.34

Table 1: Material properties.

Figure 7: Crack propagation behavior (FEM result).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figs. 8 (a) and (b) show the load-displacement relations obtained by the static and impact ENF tests, respectively. The red lines show the reaction force at the loading point of the specimen, P . The blue lines show the equivalent load calculated from the surface strain above the initial crack tip, ε_{st}/D . As shown in Fig. 8 (a), the equivalent load, ε_{st}/D , agreed well with the reaction force, P . As shown in Fig. 8 (b), the reaction force, P , displayed large oscillations owing to the high-frequency vibration of the specimen. However, the equivalent load, ε_{st}/D , approximately linearly increased with the displacement, δ , before the crack onset similar to that of the static ENF test.

Figs. 9 (a) and (b) show the crack growth resistance curves (R-curves) of the Zanchor reinforced composite (Z2) and base composite (B0), respectively. The abscissa represents the crack extension, Δa , obtained by the SDT analysis. The ordinate represents the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , obtained by

the LSB formula. The red solid and blue broken lines show the results of the dynamic and static ENF tests, respectively. As shown in Fig. 9 (a), the fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , under dynamic loading was equivalent to or slightly lower than that under static loading for the base composite, B0. Conversely, as shown in Fig. 9 (b), the fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , under dynamic loading was higher than that under static loading for the Zanchor composite, Z2. Comparing the results of the Zanchor composites with those of the base composites, the mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , of the Zanchor composite was higher than that of the base composite regardless of the loading rate.

The above results demonstrated that the Zanchor process effectively improved the mode II fracture toughness at high and low loading rates. The efficiency of the reinforcement with the Zanchor process was larger at high loading rates than that at low loading rates. These trends were consistent with the reinforcement mechanism of Zanchor shown in previous studies [4]. The validity of the estimation method for the dynamic fracture toughness using the SWC, LSB, and SDT techniques was also demonstrated based on the numerical and experimental results.

Figure 8: Load-displacement relation (Zanchor composite, Z2).

Figure 9: Effect of the loading rate on the fracture toughness.

5 CONCLUSION

The mode II fracture behavior of the Zanchor composite under impact loading was investigated to confirm the effectiveness of the Zanchor reinforcement process under high loading rates. To obtain the dynamic energy release rate, the SWC technique and LSB formula were employed. SDT analysis was proposed to estimate the crack growth behavior under high loading rates. The results are summarized below.

- (1) The crack propagation behavior in the ENF test was accurately estimated from the surface strain near the crack tip of the specimen using SDT analysis.
- (2) The mode II energy release rate under impact loading was evaluated using the SWC technique and LSB formula.
- (3) The Zanchor process improved the mode II fracture toughness under both static and impact loading.
- (4) The efficiency of the reinforcement with the Zanchor process was higher under impact loading than under static loading.
- (5) The mode II fracture toughness increased with increasing loading rate in the Zanchor composites; however, it decreased in the base composites.

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